

CERTIFICATE

This certificate is hereby awarded to

Murilo Henrique Moreira

For the best oral presentation entitled as

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through Macro Thermogravimetry and Numerical Simulations*

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Victor Carlos Pandolfelli

Rotating Chairperson of 2023
Victor Carlos Pandolfelli
Federal University of Sao Carlos